

Descriptions of two new species of *Oxychilus* (Gastropoda: Oxychilidae) from Portugal and Spain, with notes on variability of *O. navarricus* (Bourguignat, 1870) in Spain

Descripción de dos nuevas especies de *Oxychilus* (Gastropoda: Oxychilidae) de Portugal y España, con notas sobre la variabilidad de *O. navarricus* (Bourguignat, 1870) en España

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ABSTRACT

Three Iberian populations of *Oxychilus* discovered over the past decade are described, all of which are similar to *O. navarricus* (syn. *O. helveticus* (Blum, 1881)) in shell characters. Populations from a single locality in Estremadura (western central Portugal) and from Prov. Huelva (SW. Spain) were found to differ from *O. navarricus* in lacking the black edge to the mantle and lacking the characteristic smell of raw garlic emitted when the animals are handled. Study of the genital anatomy revealed that these populations differ from each other and from *O. navarricus* in structures on the inner wall of the proximal part of the penis. Hence, they are named as *O. alpedrizensis* n. sp. and *O. aracenensis* n. sp. respectively.

A third population from the base of a sink-hole in limestone hills near Ranero in Prov. Vizcaya (Basque Country, north-west Spain) resembled *O. navarricus* in emitting the smell of garlic and in some shell characters but differed in its shells having much lower spires and a keeled periphery to the inner whorls, lacking the whitish base to the shell, and having paler mantle coloration. Nevertheless, they did not differ from *O. navarricus* in genital anatomy, characteristic specimens of that species were present nearby above the sink-hole, and one specimen from the sink-hole had a high shell spire but pale mantle colour. Consequently, the sink-hole population is regarded as representing a striking localised form conspecific with *O. navarricus*.

RESUMO

Três populações Ibéricas de *Oxychilus* descobertas ao longo da década passada são descritas, todas similares a *O. navarricus* (sinónimo *O. helveticus* (Blum, 1881)) nas características da concha. Populações de uma única localidade na Estremadura (Centro Oeste de Portugal) e da Província de Huelva (Sudoeste de Espanha) foram consideradas diferentes de *O. navarricus* por não terem a orla negra do manto e não terem o cheiro característico de alho cru que é emitido quando os animais são manuseados. Estudo da anatomia genital revelou que estas populações diferem entre si e de *O. navarricus* em estruturas na

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parede interna da parte proximal do pénis. Portanto, são nomeadas como *O. alpedrizensis* n. sp. e *O. aracenensis* n. sp. respetivamente.

Uma terceira população da base de um sumidouro nas colinas calcárias perto de Ranero na Província da Vizcaya (País Vasco, Noroeste de Espanha) parecem-se com *O. navarricus* pela emissão de cheiro a alho e em algumas características da concha, mas diferem nas suas conchas por terem uma muito mais baixa espira e uma periferia em quilha para as voltas internas, faltando a base esbranquiçada para a concha, e tendo a coloração do manto mais pálida. Mesmo assim, não divergem de *O. navarricus* em anatomia genital, espécimes típicos desta espécie estavam presentes nas proximidades acima do sumidouro, e um espécime do sumidouro tinha uma espira alta, mas uma coloração do manto pálida. Consequentemente, a população do sumidouro é considerada como representando uma marcante forma localizada, conspécifica com *O. navarricus*.

RESUMEN

Se describen tres poblaciones ibéricas de *Oxychilus* descubiertas en la última década, todas similares a *O. navarricus* (sin. *O. helveticus* (Blum, 1881)) en las características de la concha. Por un lado, las poblaciones encontradas en una única localidad de Extremadura (centro oeste de Portugal) y en la provincia de Huelva (suroeste de España) se diferencian de *O. navarricus* en que carecían del borde negro del manto y del característico olor a ajo crudo que se desprende cuando los animales son manipulados. El estudio de la anatomía genital reveló que estas poblaciones diferían entre sí y de *O. navarricus* en las estructuras de la pared interna de la parte proximal del pene. Por consiguiente, pasan a denominarse como *O. alpedrizensis* n. sp. y *O. aracenensis* n. sp., respectivamente.

Por otro lado, la tercera población encontrada en la base de la dolina en colinas de piedra caliza cerca de Ranero, Vizcaya (País Vasco, noroeste de España), se asemejaba a *O. navarricus* en la emisión de olor a ajo y en algunas características de la concha, pero se distinguía en que sus conchas tenían espiras mucho más bajas y una periferia aquilada en las vueltas internas, carecían de base blanquecina de la concha y tenían una coloración del manto más pálida. Sin embargo, no diferían de *O. navarricus* en la anatomía genital. Los especímenes típicos de esta especie se hallaban presentes por encima de la dolina, y un espécimen de la dolina tenía una espira alta, pero un manto pálido. En consecuencia, se considera que la población de la dolina representa una forma localizada llamativa conspécifica con *O. navarricus*.

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KEY WORDS: Land-snails, *Oxychilus*, Oxychilidae, Iberian Peninsula, shell characters, genital anatomy, mantle coloration, garlic smell.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: Caracóis, *Oxychilus*, Oxychilidae, Península Ibérica, características da concha, anatomia genital, coloração do manto, cheiro a alho.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Caracoles terrestres, *Oxychilus*, Oxychilidae, Península Ibérica, característica de la concha, anatomía genital, coloración del manto, olor a ajo.

INTRODUCTION

Species of the land-snail genus *Oxychilus* are often difficult to identify because reliable shell characters are few and sometimes subtle (cf. CADEVALL & OROZCO, 2016). RIEDEL & VILELLA (1968) reviewed

the Spanish species and genital anatomy provided RIEDEL (1980, 1998) with additional characters to subdivide the genus in his major review of the Zonitidae, in which *Oxychilus* was formerly classified.

However, since it may be difficult to obtain living adult material for anatomical studies in dry regions of southern Europe, the identity of various local populations has remained difficult to establish.

FALKNER, RIPKEN & FALKNER (2002: 124-125) found that *Hyalinia alliaria* subsp. *cantabrica* Westerlund, 1883 (= *Oxychilus helveticus cantabricus* sensu RIEDEL, 1970: 389-390, 1980: 89) should be regarded as a synonym of *Zonites navarricus* Bourguignat, 1870. Thus, the species treated prior to 2002 as *Oxychilus helveticus* (Blum, 1881) should become *Oxychilus navarricus* (Bourguignat, 1870). As pointed out by FALKNER, RIPKEN & FALKNER (2002) and WELTER-SCHULTES (2012: 388), the species has three disjunct centres of distribution, respectively (1) in the Jura of E. France and W. Switzerland, (2) around the English Channel in Belgium, N. France, Great Britain and, as a local introduction, Ireland, and (3) in SW. France and NW. Spain. RIEDEL (1998) treated the populations from throughout this range as monotypic, but FALKNER, RIPKEN & FALKNER (2002: 125) maintained *O. n. helveticus* as a subspecies based on "nos propres observations", but without stating or discussing differences between the subspecies. GIUSTI & MANGANELLI (2002: 461-466) studied British, French (Pyrenean), Swiss and Spanish specimens without finding any distinctive differences. Likewise, our samples from populations in Great Britain, SW. France and NW. Spain all seem similar in characters of the shell, body coloration and distal genital anatomy, so we also treat *O. navarricus* as monotypic here.

ALTONAGA (1991) provided extensive data on the shells and genital anatomy of numerous populations of *O. navarricus* (as *O. helveticus*) from NW. Spain, thus providing a detailed understanding of the wide variability in its characters. That study supported recognition by him of two additional species from NW. Spain, *O. anjana* described by ALTONAGA (1986) and *O. basajauna* described by ALTONAGA (1990). Those newly discovered species differ only slightly from each other and *O. navarri-*

cus in shell characters, but show more decisive differences in penial anatomy, especial in the structure of the internal wall of the proximal part of the penis (see Key below).

GIUSTI & MANGANELLI (2002) confirmed and added to the descriptions by ALTONAGA (1991) for specimens from NW. Spain and established that British, French Pyrenean and Swiss specimens all share similar genital anatomy to that he described. They also clarified anatomical data on *O. alliarius* (Miller, 1822) and pointed out that this species and *O. navarricus* (as *O. helveticus*) should be placed in *Oxychilus s. str.* rather than recognising subgenus *Ortizius* Forcart, 1957 (with type species *Hyalinia (Polita) helvetica* Blum, 1881), which was treated as valid by RIEDEL (1998).

New discoveries from fieldwork over the past decade have led to preparation of the present account, which considers three Iberian populations of *Oxychilus* which are most similar to *O. navarricus* in shell characters. Two separate populations from a locality in Estremadura (western central Portugal) and from Prov. Huelva (south-west Spain) (Fig. 1) were found to differ from *O. navarricus* in lacking the black edge to the mantle and lacking the characteristic smell of raw garlic emitted when the animals are handled. The latter is better known as a characteristic of *O. alliarius*, for which TURTON (1840: 168) used the English name "Garlic Snail" which is still in use today, and commented (*ibid.*, p. 169) on it "emitting a strong smell of garlic when irritated"; the scientific epithet *alliarius* also refers to this trait, since *Allium sativum* is the cultivated garlic. Other common congeners including *O. cellarius* (O.F. Müller, 1774) and *O. draparnaudi* (Beck, 1837) do not produce the garlic smell. Study of the genital anatomy of the Estremadura and Huelva populations revealed they differ from each other and from *O. navarricus* in structures on the inner wall of the proximal part of the penis. Hence, these are named as new species here.

A third population from the base of a limestone sink-hole in Prov. Vizcaya

Figure 1. Distribution of some *Oxychilus* species in Portugal and Spain mapped in 10-kilometre squares of the UTM grid. The approximate range of *O. navarricus* within Spain has grey shading.

Figura 1. Distribución de algunas especies de Oxychilus en Portugal y España, mapa en cuadrículas UTM de 10 x10 Km. La distribución aproximada de O. navarricus en España se muestra sombreada en gris. La distribución aproximada de O. navarricus en España se muestra sombreada en gris.

(Basque Country, NW. Spain) (Fig. 1) resembled *O. navarricus* in emitting the garlic smell and in some shell characters, but differed conspicuously in having shells with much lower spires and a keeled periphery to the inner whorls, lacking the whitish base to the shell, and having paler mantle coloration. However, they did not differ from *O. navarricus* in genital anatomy, typical specimens of that species were present close by outside the sink-hole, and one specimen from within the sink-hole had a high shell spire but pale mantle colour. Consequently, as discussed below, the sink-hole population is regarded as representing a striking localised form conspecific with *O. navarricus*.

METHODS

Specimens were collected by hand, commonly by turning over logs and rocks in moist wooded habitats. Localities and altitudes were recorded using

hand-held GPS accurate to within 10 metres or less. Habitat notes (including bedrock type and vegetation) and associated Mollusca were recorded at the sites.

Living specimens of the Portuguese and Cantabrian populations were taken home and kept in captivity to allow study of body coloration, etc. Specimens of all the species studied were killed by immersion in water overnight, then preserved in 80% IMS. In some cases, the bodies were pulled from the shells and kept separately from the shells, which were dried. The distal genitalia were removed from the bodies for detailed study and preparation of drawings.

Studies of shells and the bodies of live snails were made using Meiji RZ series stereomicroscopes, with intense illumination from a Schott KL 1500 light source via twin fibre-optic swan necks. Magnifications of up to $\times 56$ were used to study microsculpture and the structure of the interior of penis. Drawings were prepared using a Meiji drawing tube.

Dissections of the genitalia confirmed the impression that shells of adults were often not distinguishable from those of subadults. This is because the peristome edge remains thin and plane throughout and a membranous uncalcified fringe to it may not always be apparent in subadults, perhaps due to pauses in shell growth. Consequently, the lower size limit for selection of shells to be measured was approximate, being judged from the small proportion of dissected specimens. Because of this source of uncertainty, we do not present analyses of the measurements using means and standard deviations since these could be misleading.

Shell height was measured strictly perpendicular to the measurement of shell breadth, as the maximum from the top of the protoconch to a line level with the lowest part of the outer basal edge of the peristome. The measurements were made using an eyepiece graticule and were found to be reproducible to $\pm ca$ 0.005 mm for shell breadth but only to $\pm ca$ 0.01 mm for shell height, where larger variations are likely to arise from slight tilting of the shells.

Scarcity of live-collected adult specimens restricted the opportunity for us to fully explore the internal anatomy of organs of the distal genitalia. Hence, if additional material becomes available in future, it would be worthwhile to obtain fuller descriptions of the relative position of the epiphallic pore and any internal structures in the area around it. The present

account rather arbitrarily regards the distal penis as the portion covered by the penial sheath, whereas in other *Oxychilus* the internal structures show that the distal part of the penis extends further proximally, so that future studies should seek to delimit this more precisely.

Abbreviations: Data on specimens: leg., collected by; n, number (sample size); sh, shells; spm, specimens preserved in industrial methylated spirit (70-80 %).

Morphology & anatomy: AB, shell aperture breadth; AH, shell aperture height (perpendicular to AB); B, greatest diameter (breadth) of shell; H, height of shell; U, width of umbilicus; see legends to Figs 4 and 5 for abbreviations used therein for parts of distal genitalia.

Locality coordinates: hectad, 10 km square of UTM grid designated using MGRS notation; MGRS, Military Grid Reference coordinates, derived from the UTM system; NGR, British grid references (Ordnance Survey grid); UTM, Universal Transverse Mercator mapping grid.

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Institutional & other collections: CJFMA, Collection of JFMA; CRM, Collection of RCM; HC, Holyoak Collection (now owned by DTH); MNCN, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid.

RESULTS AND TAXONOMY

Family OXYCHILIDAE Hesse, 1927 (1879)

Genus *Oxychilus* Fitzinger, 1833

Oxychilus alpedrizensis n. sp. D. Holyoak & R. Mendes

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Types. *Holotype*: Portugal • 1 sh (breadth 10.41 mm) and soft parts in industrial methylated spirit (70-80 %); Estremadura, Leiria district, Alcobaça, Near Parque de Lazer, Nascentes das Loureiras (S. of Rua da Fonte), 0.8 km due W. of roundabout in Alpedriz village; MGRS 29SND03558647; 36-37 m alt; 9 Nov. 2013; DTH P344 & RCM leg.; MNCN 15.05/200178. *Paratypes*: Portugal • 1 sh and soft parts in industrial methylated spirit (70-80 %), 2 spm (immature); same data as for holotype;

Holyoak Collection. • 7 sh, 4 soft parts in industrial methylated spirit (70-80 %); same locality as holotype; 5 Mar. 2014; DTH P351A & RCM leg.; Holyoak Collection • 12 sh (3 from snails kept alive for several weeks); same locality as holotype; 9 May 2015, DTH & GAH P423B leg.; Holyoak Collection. • 2 sh; same locality as holotype; 9 May 2015; DTH & GAH P423B leg.; Collection of RCM. **Other material examined:** • 4 immature specimens; same locality as holotype; 5 Mar. 2014; DTH P351A & RCM leg., Holyoak Collection.

Type locality: Near Parque de Lazer, Nascentes das Loureiras (S. of Rua da Fonte), 0.8 km due W. of roundabout in Alpedriz village [Alcobaça, Leiria district], Estremadura, Portugal. MGRS: 29SND03558647 (hectad 29SND08), 36-37 m alt.

Derivation of name: Based on the type locality, near Alpedriz village.

Description:

Shell (Fig. 2A): 28 examined, all from the type-locality. Depressed-convex above, flatter below, with body-whorl descending and widening, especially in last half-whorl. Measurements ($n = 12$), H 4.08-5.78 mm, B 9.66-11.70 mm, H/B 0.39-0.49, with 4.1-4.5 whorls. Whorls rounded, the largest shells with body-whorl distinctly flattened below towards aperture. Sutures rather shallow, distinctly impressed as narrow channel showing as double-line in dorsal view. Umbilicus moderately narrow, 1.36-1.97 mm (U/B 0.13-0.17; $n = 12$), deep, exposing whorls of spire internally, symmetrical except in largest shells where body-whorl slightly more divergent, very narrowly overlapped by innermost end of peristome. Aperture broadly oval-pyriform with outline interrupted by penultimate whorl; shape rendered somewhat asymmetrical because curvature of lower edge less marked than that of upper and (especially) outer edges (AH 3.74-4.35 mm, AB 4.63-5.51 mm, AH/AB 0.76-0.81, $n = 12$). Peristome thin, plane except at and near umbilicus where slightly reflected. Shell thin; when mature remaining sub-transparent dorsally and translucent ventrally; bright light brown above; below whitish pale-brown around umbilicus, shading gradually to bright light brown on outer half of body-whorl. Periostracum glossy above and below; protoconch smooth; teleoconch appearing smooth and shiny; magnification reveals delicate and rather irregular spiral microsculpture above and below; transverse growth ridges low, rounded and irregular.

External characters of body: Head and dorsal part of body dark grey or

deep slightly bluish-grey, including top of tail; sides light grey below; middle of body below shell pale grey; sole of foot mid-grey with middle one-third of width paler; most of mantle light grey, lacking any wide blackish band in outer part; mantle edge inside shell dark; line on mantle along suture of body-whorl very dark (near-black) for one-third of whorl; upper whorls of spire brown, visible by translucence. Living animals do not produce a smell of fresh garlic when touched or handled.

Genital anatomy (Figs 4A, 5A): Six dissected (four of these adult or near adult, including one having poorly developed penis in body cavity containing parasitic worm five times length of snail's body). Features not apparent from figures: genital orifice on right-hand side of forepart of body, somewhat below base of right ommatophore and one-third of distance back towards inner edge of mantle-collar; right ommatophore retractor passes between distal parts of penis and of vagina; penis retractor muscle long and slender, extending proximally to join body wall.

Internal structure of proximal part of penis studied in two adult specimens (Fig. 5A). Both have inside of wall of proximal penis with eight (locally nine) rows of aligned papillae, which are rounded to oval in cross-section, the rows closely spaced so the papillae are tightly appressed to each other. The papillae decrease in size distally as penis becomes narrower as it approaches proximal part of penis sheath. The papillae are also smaller along a small part of the wider section of the proximal penis, on the same side as exit from epiphallus and distally to it.

Figure 2. Shells of some Iberian *Oxychilus* species. A: *O. alpedrizensis* (paratype, in HC, B 11.61 mm, ca 0.5 km W. of Alpedriz, Estremadura, Portugal, 9 Nov. 2013, site P344); B: *O. aracenensis* (paratype, in HC, B 10.41 mm, Fuente Santa, La Nava, Prov. Huelva, Spain, 9 Nov. 2020); C: “Ranero form” of *O. navarricus* (in HC, B 10.80 mm, ca 1 km W. of Ranero, Prov. Vizcaya, Spain, 11 May 2011, site E154 from inside sink-hole); D: typical form of *O. navarricus* (in HC, B 10.54 mm, ca 1 km W. of Ranero, Prov. Vizcaya, Spain, 11 May 2011, site E154 from outside sink-hole).

Figura 2. Conchas de algunas especies ibéricas de Oxychilus. A: O. alpedrizensis (paratipo, en HC, B 11,61 mm, aprox. 0,5 km al O. de Alpedriz, Estremadura, Portugal, 9 Nov. 2013, sitio P344); B: O. aracenensis (paratipo, en HC, B 10,41 mm, Fuente Santa, La Nava, Huelva, España, 9 Nov. 2020); C: O. navarricus “forma Ranero” (en HC, B 10,80 mm, aprox. 1 km al O. de Ranero, Vizcaya, España, 11 May 2011, sitio E154 desde el interior de la dolina); D: forma típica de O. navarricus (en HC, B 10,54 mm, aprox. 1 km al O. de Ranero, Vizcaya, España, 11 May 2011, sitio E154 desde el exterior de la dolina).

Comparisons: Resembles *O. aracensis* and differs from *O. navarricus* in lacking black band on front of mantle and lacking the garlic smell of live snails. Shells of *O. alpedrizensis* are generally similar to those of some forms of *O. navarricus*, but often have stronger spiral microsculpture. They also resemble shells of *O. aracensis*, but umbilicus is relatively wider, aperture usually more oval and narrower (AH/AB often lower), number of whorls often lower; whitish coloration on underside of shell more distinct. Distinct from all Iberian congeners with similar shells in the sculpture on interior of wall of proxi-

mal part of penis having rows of discrete papillae that are tightly packed together. *O. aracensis* has rows of papillae that are more widely spaced, and it also differs more obviously in having the proximal part of its penis much longer than in *O. aracensis* (with length $>7 \times$ width cf. $<3 \times$ width).

Ecology: Known only from the type locality, on steep bank bordering upper edge of a track, low on side of small valley. The bank with limestone rock exposed in small areas, elsewhere with cover of grasses and herbs, part-shaded by edge of deciduous woodland above.

Oxychilus aracensis n. sp. D. Holyoak & J.F. Martín

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Types. *Holotype:* Spain • 1 sh (breadth 10.48 mm) and soft parts in industrial methylated spirit (70-80 %); Huelva province, Río Múrtigas, La Nava; UTM 29S 699451 4201677, MGRS 29SPC99450; 11 May 2021; JFMA leg.; MNCN 15.05/200179. *Paratypes:* • 1 sh and soft parts in industrial methylated spirit (70-80 %); same data as for holotype; Holyoak Collection • 1 sh; Huelva province, Galaroza, Barranco de la Fuente del Aliso; MGRS 29SQB031599; 29 Oct. 2020, 16 May 2021; Collection of JFMA • 2 spm; Huelva province, Galaroza, Barranco de la Fuente del Aliso; MGRS 29SQB031599; 16 May 2021; JFMA leg.; Holyoak Collection • 1 sh; Huelva province, Cortelazor, Ribera de Huelva; 9 Nov. 2020; Collection of JFMA • 1 sh; Huelva province, Fuenteheridos, Ribera Río Múrtigas; MGRS 29SQB058098; 9 Nov. 2020; Collection of JFMA • 1 sh; Huelva province, La Nava, Fuente Santa; MGRS 29SQC005100; 9 Nov. 2020; Collection of JFMA • 2 sh; Huelva province, La Nava, Fuente Santa; MGRS 29SQC005100; 9 Nov. 2020; JFMA leg.; Holyoak Collection • 1 sh; Huelva province, Cortegana, Rivera de Chanza; UTM 29SPB891498; 31 Dec. 2020; Collection of JFMA • 1 sh; Huelva province, Almonaster la Real (municipality), Ribera de Almonaster la Real; UTM 29SPB948193; 31 Dec. 2020, 22 May 2021; Collection of JFMA • 1 sh; Huelva province, Almonaster la Real, Barranco de Los Romeros; UTM 29SPB975196; 22 May 2021; Collection of JFMA • 1 sh; Huelva province, Almonaster la Real, Tributario del barranco de Los Romeros; UTM 29SPB966596; 22 May 2021; Collection of JFMA • 1 sh; Huelva province, Almonaster la Real, Canaleja, Tributario del barranco de la Esparragosa; UTM 29S951996; 22 May 2021; Collection of JFMA.

Type locality: by Río Múrtigas, La Nava (Prov. Huelva, Spain), UTM: 29S 699451 4201677 (MGRS: 29SPC99450167; hectad 29SPC90), 475 m alt.

Derivation of name: From the type locality in Sierra de Aracena.

Description:

Shell (Fig. 2B): 16 examined, from 10 localities. Depressed-convex above, flatter below with body-whorl descending and widening, especially in last one-third of whorl. Measurements, H 4.4-6.4 mm (n = 13), B 8.2-11.5 mm (n = 14), H/B 0.46-0.56 (n = 13), with 4.3-5.5 (n = 13) whorls at maturity. Whorls rounded, the body-whorl distinctly flattened below towards aperture. Sutures rather shallow, distinctly impressed as narrow

channel showing as double-line in dorsal view. Umbilicus relatively narrow, 0.92-1.47 mm (U/B 0.10-0.13; n = 14), deep, exposing whorls of spire internally, symmetrical, except that body-whorl slightly more divergent, very narrowly overlapped by innermost end of peristome. Aperture broadly rounded-pyriform, with outline interrupted by penultimate whorl; curvature of lower edge slightly less marked than that of upper edge, both of these much less curved than

Figure 3. Living animals of *Oxychilus* species showing body coloration. A: *O. aracenensis* (Barranco de la Fuente del Aliso, Galaroza, Prov. Huelva, Spain, 29 October 2020; © JFMA); B: characteristic *O. navarricus* (photo: Hertfordshire, England, March 1978; ©DTH). C, D: “Ranero form” of *O. navarricus* (ca 1 km W. of Ranero, Prov. Vizcaya, Spain, 11 May 2011, site E154 from inside sink-hole; photo 8 July 2011 from snail kept in captivity ©DTH).

Figura 3. Animales vivos de las especies de Oxychilus que muestran su coloración corporal. A: O. aracenensis (barranco de la Fuente del Aliso, Galaroza, Huelva, España, 29 Octubre 2020, © JFMA); B: O. navarricus típico (foto: Hertfordshire, Inglaterra, Marzo 1978; ©DTH). C, D: O. navarricus “forma Ranero” (aprox. 1 km al O. de Ranero, Vizcaya, España, 11 Mayo 2011, sitio E154 desde el interior de la dolina; foto 8 Julio 2011 de un caracol en cautiverio ©DTH).

outer edge (AH 3.85-5.16 mm, AB 4.82-6.11 mm, AH/AB 0.79-0.88, $n = 14$). Peristome thin, plane except at and near umbilicus, where slightly reflected. Shell thin when mature, remaining sub-transparent dorsally and translucent ventrally; bright light brown above; below mainly pale brown (almost whitish) around umbilicus, shading gradually to bright light brown on outer half of body-whorl. Periostracum glossy above and below; protoconch smooth (somewhat corroded in adult shells); teleoconch appearing smooth and shiny; magnifica-

tion reveals delicate and rather irregular spiral microsculpture above and below; transverse growth ridges low, rounded and irregular.

External characters of body: Described in detail from two specimens, one paler than other; front and top of head and dorsum of forepart of body mid-grey (slightly bluish); top of tail same mid-grey in darker specimen, palest grey to whitish in paler specimen; flanks mid-grey almost throughout in darker specimen (whitish only in part nearest shell aperture), whitish shading to pale grey in uppermost

parts in paler specimen; foot-fringe pale grey in dark specimen, whitish in lighter specimen; sole of foot light grey with irregular whitish central band in darker specimen, palest grey with whitish central band in paler specimen; most of mantle light brown lacking any wide blackish band in outer part; front edge of mantle light grey with ill-defined darker outer zone; organs inside spire light brown, visible through translucent shell. A third individual that was photographed alive (Fig. 3A) appears to have been a darker individual than either of those described from specimens, but again lacking any well defined black band on the front edge of the mantle. Living animals do not produce a smell of fresh garlic when touched or handled.

Genital anatomy (Figs 4B, 5B): Two adult snails dissected. Features not apparent from figures: genital orifice high on right flank of forepart of body, behind base of right ommatophore, about midway back to front edge of mantle collar; right ommatophore retractor passes between distal parts of penis and of vagina; penis retractor muscle long and slender, extending proximally to join connective tissue close to proximal part of spermiduct (darker specimen drawn had part of retractor muscle forming two separate subparallel strands; paler specimen had the muscle undivided in the usual manner for *Oxychilus*).

Internal structure of proximal part of penis studied in one adult paratype (Fig. 5B). It has inside of wall of proximal penis bearing seven rows of aligned papillae; the papillae are mainly oval in cross-section, blunt-topped, joined basally by a thin narrow ridge; the rows are clearly separated so their papillae are mainly not in contact.

Comparisons (see Key below): Resembles *O. alpedrizensis* and differs from *O. navarricus* in lacking black band on front of mantle and lacking the garlic smell of live snails. Shells of *O. aracenensis* are generally similar to those of some forms of *O. navarricus*, but often have stronger spiral microsculpture. They also resemble shells of *O. alpedrizensis*, but umbilicus is relatively narrower, aperture usually rounder and broader (AH/AB often greater), number of whorls often higher; whitish coloration on underside of shell less distinct. Distinct from all Iberian congeners with similar shells in the sculpture on interior of wall of proximal part of penis having rows of discrete papillae separated by gaps. *O. alpedrizensis* has rows of papillae that are tightly packed together and it also differs more obviously in having the proximal part of its penis much shorter (with length $<3 \times$ width cf. $>7 \times$ width).

Ecology: At type-locality frequent in groves of riparian gallery woodland of *Populus nigra*, living in humid, shady places without insolation, among herbaceous vegetation, plant litter and other decomposing ground material, or beneath logs and stones. The overall range of the new species (see localities listed above) is in the Sierra de Aracena and Picos de Aroche Natural Parks of Prov. Huelva, comprising ranges of hills and low mountains (200-780 m alt.), composed mainly of dark-coloured slates and quartzites. The regional annual rainfall exceeds 1000 mm and average mean temperatures range from 7°-25°C. Valleys of three rivers (Guadalquivir, Guadiana, and Odiel) drain the natural park and these support the riparian woodlands in which *O. aracenensis* appears to be widespread.

“Ranero form” of *Oxychilus navarricus* (Bourguignat, 1870), with low-spired shell

Material examined of form with low spired shell: Spain • 6 sh; Vizcaya province, municipality of Valle de Carranza, ca 1 km W of Ranero, 4.5 km N of Concha; MGRS 30TVN693903; ca 447 m alt; 14-15 Jun. 2007; from litter at base of a deep shaded hollow (sink-hole) in limestone slope, the surrounding areas with herb-rich grassland and patches of scrub; GAH & DTH E40 leg.;

Figure 4. Anatomy of distal genitalia of Iberian *Oxychilus* species. A: *O. alpedrizensis* (Holotype, in MNCN, ca 0.5 km W. of Alpedriz, Estremadura, Portugal, 9 Nov. 2013, site P344); B: *O. aracenensis* (Paratype, in HC, Río Múrtigas, Prov. Huelva, Spain, 11 May 2021); C: “Ranero form” of *O. navarricus* (in HC, ca 1 km W. of Ranero, Prov. Vizcaya, Spain, 11 May 2011, site E154 from inside sink-hole); D: Typical *O. navarricus* (in HC, W. of Culdrose, W. Cornwall, England). Abbreviations, at: genital atrium; bc: bursa copulatrix; bw: body wall; dbc: duct of bursa copulatrix; dp: distal part of penis (mainly within penis sheath); ep: epiphallus; f: flagellum; fo: free oviduct; pp: proximal part of penis; prm: penis retractor muscle; sod: spermioviduct; v: vagina; vd: vas deferens; vg: vaginal gland.

Figura 4. Anatomía de la genitalia distal de especies ibéricas de *Oxychilus*. A: *O. alpedrizensis* (Holotipo, en MNCN, aprox. 0.5 km al O. de Alpedriz, Estremadura, Portugal, 9 Nov. 2013, sitio P344); B: *O. aracenensis* (Paratipo, en HC, Río Múrtigas, Prov. Huelva, España, 11 Mayo 2021); C: *O. navarricus* “forma Ranero” (en HC, aprox. 1 km al O. de Ranero, Prov. Vizcaya, España, 11 Mayo 2011, sitio E154 desde el interior de la dolina); D: *O. navarricus* típico (en HC, O. de Culdrose, O. de Cornwall, Inglaterra). Abreviaturas, at: atrio genital; bc: bolsa copulatrix; bw: pared del cuerpo; dbc: conducto de la bolsa copulatrix; dp: parte distal del pene (principalmente dentro de la vaina del pene); ep: epifalo; f: flagelo; fo: oviducto libre; pp: parte proximal del pene; prm: músculo retractor del pene; sod: espermioviducto; v: vagina; vd: vaso deferente; vg: glándula vaginal.

Holyoak collection • 6 sh, 2 soft parts preserved in industrial methylated spirit (70-80 %), 1 spm (immature) (1 of these sh + soft parts from sink hole with higher shell spire, described as “variant individual” below); Vizcaya province, municipality of Valle de Carranza, ca 1 km W of Ranero, 4.5 km N of Concha; MGRS 30TVN693903; ca 447 m alt; 11 May 2011; DTH & GAH E154 leg.; Holyoak collection.

Material examined of *O. navarricus* with typical high-spired shells: Spain • 1 sh, 2 spm (1 immature); Vizcaya province, municipality of Valle de Carranza, ca 1 km W of Ranero, 4.5 km N of Concha; MGRS 30TVN693903; ca 447 m alt; 11 May 2011; from outside sink-hole in limestone slope, the surrounding areas with herb-rich grassland and patches of scrub; DTH & GAH E154 leg.; Holyoak collection • 1 spm; Santander province, SE. of Guriezo, just SE. of Llaguno; MGRS 30TVN786940; 252 m alt.; 10 May 2011; from road-cutting, below limestone crag & deciduous woodland on slope; GAH & DTH E153 leg.; Holyoak collection. France • 4 spm; Dept. Pyrénées-Atlantiques, Grotte de Sare; MGRS 30TXN15879160; 220 m alt.; 7 May 2011; rocky limestone slope with cover of deciduous woodland; GAH & DTH F146 leg.; Holyoak collection. England • 7 sh; W. Cornwall, SW. of Helston; MGRS 30UUA366517 [NGR SW652269]; 2 Jan. 1999; bank beside lane with thick *Hedera*, under deciduous trees; GAH leg.; Holyoak collection • 8 sh; W. Cornwall, SW. of Gwedna; MGRS 30UUA316568 [NGR SW603320]; 11 Feb. 2000; deciduous woodland on old mine workings; GAH leg.; Holyoak collection • 15 sh and soft parts preserved in industrial methylated spirit (70-80 %); W. Cornwall, W. of Culdrose; MGRS 30UUA382491 [NGR SW668243]; 24 Mar. 2003; vegetation on flushed stream bank and in woodland; GAH leg.; Holyoak collection.

Description:

Shell (Fig. 2C): 12 examined, from same locality within a single sink-hole (only 4 of shells were fresh: 2 adults and 2 immatures). One variant individual is described separately below. Very depressed-convex above, slightly flattened below with outer half of body-whorl descending and widening towards aperture. Measurements (n = 6), H 4.0-4.4 mm, B 8.57-10.88 mm, H/B 0.38-0.43, with 4.0-4.4 whorls. Whorls rounded above and below, the immature shells and inner half of body-whorl of adults with definite blunt keel above mid-line of periphery, that disappears towards aperture in adults. Sutures shallow, impressed as channel, showing as double line in dorsal view. Umbilicus rather narrow on small shells, somewhat larger on largest shells, 0.95-1.56 mm wide (U/B 0.11-0.15; n = 6), deep, exposing whorls of spire, symmetrical internally but asymmetrical where body wall diverges, not overlapped by innermost end of peristome. Aperture oval-pyriform, outline interrupted by penultimate whorl, with strongly curved outer margin, weakly curved dorsal margin, lower margin moderately curved except where sharply inflexed near umbilicus. Peristome thin, plane, scarcely reflected near umbilicus. Shell thin, subtransparent in immatures, remaining translucent

when adult; bright light brown above, slightly paler below (lacking whitish around umbilicus). Periostracum glossy above and below; protoconch smooth; teleoconch appearing smooth and shiny; magnification reveals only faint and distant traces of delicate irregular spiral microsculpture above and below; transverse growth ridges very low, rounded and irregular.

Shell of variant individual: One adult snail collected alive from the sink-hole differs from the other 12 shells studied. It shows characters intermediate between the 12 low-spired shells from the sink hole and 2 typical adult *O. navarricus* from adjacent slopes outside the sink-hole. The variant individual has H 4.49 mm, B 9.80 mm, H/B 0.46, AH 3.95 mm, AB 4.56 mm, AH/AB 0.87, U 1.22 mm, U/B 0.13, 4.1 shell whorls; thus it has the spire higher than in the other 12 shells from the sink-hole; it also has the suture slightly deeper and the underside of the shell whitish unlike the 12 others.

The two typical shells from slopes outside the sink-hole within <50 m from it (empty adult shell: Fig 2D; other specimen was collected alive) have H 4.76, 5.03 mm, B 10.54, 10.99 mm, H/B 0.45, 0.46, both with 4.5 whorls; both of these shells lack a peripheral keel and both have white coloration on the underside.

Figure 5. Drawings of structures on the inner wall of the proximal part of the penis in Iberian *Oxychilus* species, from same specimens as used for Figure 4. A: *O. alpedrizensis*; B: *O. aracensis*; C: "Ranero form" of *O. navarricus*; D: Typical *O. navarricus* from Cornwall, England. Abbreviations additional to those defined in legend to Figure 4, ls: semi-schematic longitudinal section of wall of proximal part of penis; ts: semi-schematic transverse section of wall of proximal part of penis.

Figura 5. Dibujo de las estructuras de la pared interna de la parte proximal del pene de las especies ibéricas de *Oxychilus*, de los mismos ejemplares que se utilizaron para la Figura 4. A: *O. alpedrizensis*; B: *O. aracensis*; C: *O. navarricus* "forma Ranero"; D: *O. navarricus* típico de Cornwall, Inglaterra. Abreviaturas adicionales a las definidas en la leyenda de la Figura 4, ls: sección longitudinal semi-esquemática de la pared de la parte proximal del pene; ts: sección transversal semi-esquemática de la pared de la parte proximal del pene.

External characters of body (Fig. 3C, D): Both of the two living snails from within the sink-hole had the front edge of the mantle light grey with medium-grey to dark grey band *ca* 1.5 mm wide behind this, the remainder of the dorsal surface of the mantle being whitish with a hint of pale grey. The variant individual from within the sink-hole (see above) was similar to the other live individual in its mantle coloration. The single *O. navarricus* from outside the sink-hole which was collected alive had the band at the edge of the mantle darker, almost blackish, and the remainder of the mantle grey, as is typical of *O. navarricus* in this region (see drawing by GIUSTI & MANGANELLI 2002: 466 fig. 18) and elsewhere (Fig. 3B). Both snails from the sink-hole thus had atypically pale mantle coloration for *O. navarricus*, but with the front edge of the mantle darker-banded as usual in that species. All three living snails from Ranero (two from the sink-hole, the third from nearby) produced a strong smell of garlic when handled.

Genital anatomy: Figs 4C and 5C show the distal genitalia of a mature individual from the sink-hole that had a shell with a low spire. Based on the extensive descriptions and iconography

presented by ALTONAGA (1991), it is clear that this individual does not show any significant anatomical differences from other *O. navarricus* from NW. Spain. Its vagina is rather short and stout, but within the range of variability recorded elsewhere. The inner wall of the proximal part of its penis has seven (locally eight) wavy longitudinal ridges (Fig. 5C).

Comparisons (see Key below) and conclusions: Despite its marked difference in shell characters described above (lower spire, keeled periphery of inner whorls, lack of white coloration on underside), and pale body coloration, the form from the sink-hole does not differ anatomically from typical *O. navarricus* (cf. Figs 4D, 5D). In the absence of genetic data it initially seemed premature to conclude that the sample from the sink-hole was just a local form of *O. navarricus*, especially as typical individuals of that species were collected <50 m from the outer edge of the sink-hole. However, the presence within the sink-hole of one living “variant” with intermediate shell characters would appear to support the conclusion that a conspecific form is involved, possibly induced by growth in heavily shaded conditions with a different microclimate.

Key to Iberian species of *Oxychilus* resembling *O. navarricus* (see Figs. 2-5)

- 1. - Interior of wall of proximal part of penis with sculpture of continuous longitudinal ridges; front edge of mantle usually with black band; living snails smelling of garlic; taxa unknown in SW. Spain and (except for *O. alliaris*) unknown in Portugal 2
 - Interior of wall of proximal part of penis with sculpture of papillae which may be aligned in longitudinal rows, but which do not form continuous ridges; front edge of mantle lacking black band; living snails not smelling of garlic; taxa known only from SW. Spain and Portugal 6
- 2. - Interior of wall of proximal part of penis with 4 longitudinal ridges; adult shell breadth (B) 4.5-7.0 mm; umbilicus relatively wide (usually >1/6 of B); exposed dorsum of body usually dark bluish-grey *O. alliaris*
 - Interior of wall of proximal part of penis with 4-35 longitudinal ridges (infrequently 4); adult shell B >7.5 mm; umbilicus relatively narrow (usually <1/6 of B); exposed dorsum of body usually less dark 3
- 3. - Interior of wall of proximal part of penis with 30-35 very sinuous longitudinal ridges; endemic in NW. Spain *O. basajauna*
 - Interior of wall of proximal part of penis with <15 longitudinal ridges 4

4. - Penis small (2-3 mm) and shortly pyriform, passing abruptly into flagellum and ephallus without distinctly elongated proximal portion of penis; endemic in NW. Spain *O. anjana*
 - Penis usually longer when mature, not shortly pyriform; with elongate proximal portion well developed 5
5. - Shell with very low spire, H/B <0.46; periphery of immature shell with obvious blunt keel above midline; underside of shell lacking whitish coloration *O. navarricus* "Ranero form"
 - Shell normally with higher spire, H/B >0.45; periphery of immature shell not keeled; underside of shell typically with whitish coloration *O. navarricus*
6. - Umbilicus usually relatively narrow (U/B 0.10-0.13); proximal part of penis elongate (length >7 × width); interior of wall of proximal part of penis with rows of discrete papillae separated by gaps; known only from Prov. Huelva (SW. Spain) *O. aracenensis* n. sp.
 - Umbilicus usually relatively wider (U/B 0.13-0.17); proximal part of penis shorter and wider (length < 3 × width); interior of wall of proximal part of penis with rows of closely packed papillae; known only from western central Portugal *O. alpedrizensis* n. sp.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ALTONAGA K. 1986. A new *Oxychilus* (Gastropoda, Stylommatophora, Zonitidae) from N Iberian Peninsula. *Iberus*, 6 (2): 237-244.
- ALTONAGA K. 1990. A new species from the Iberian Peninsula: *Oxychilus* (*Ortizius*?) *basajauna* n. sp. (Pulmonata: Zonitidae). *Journal of Conchology*, 33 (5): 281-289.
- ALTONAGA K. 1991. Nuevos datos sobre *Oxychilus helveticus* (Blum, 1881) (Pulmonata, Zonitidae) en la Península Ibérica. *Iberus*, 10 (1): 1-26.
- CADEVALL J. & OROZCO A. 2016. *Caracoles y babosas de la Península Ibérica y Baleares*. Omega, Nuevas Guías de Campo Omega, Barcelona, 817 pp.
- FALKNER G., RIPKEN T.E.J. & FALKNER M. 2002. *Mollusques continentaux de France. Liste de référence annotée et bibliographie*. Patrimoines naturels, 52: 1-350, Muséum national d'histoire naturelle, Laboratoire de biologie des invertébrés marins et de malacologie, Paris, 350 pp.
- GARGOMINY O., PRIÉ V., BICHAIN J.-M., CUCHERAT X. & FONTAINE B. 2011. Liste de référence annotée des mollusques continentaux de France. *MalaCo*, 7: 307-382.
- GIUSTI F. & MANGANELLI G. 2002. Redescription of two west european *Oxychilus* species: *O. alliaris* (Miller, 1822) and *O. helveticus* (Blum, 1881) and notes on the systematics of *Oxychilus* Fitzinger, 1833 (Gastropoda: Pulmonata: Zonitidae). *Journal of Conchology*, 37 (5): 455-476.
- KERNEY M.P. & CAMERON R.A.D. 1979. *Land snails of Britain and north-west Europe*. Collins (Collins Field Guide), London, 288 pp., 24 pls. (reprinted 1987, 1994, by HarperCollins).
- RIEDEL A. 1970. Beitrag zur Kenntnis der Zonitidae (Gastropoda) der französischen Pyrenäen. *Fragmenta faunistica*, 15: 379-399.
- RIEDEL A. 1980. *Genera Zonitidarum. Diagnosen supraspezifischer Taxa der Familie Zonitidae* W. Backhuys, Rotterdam, 197 pp., 2 pls.

- RIEDEL A. 1998. *Genera Zonitidarum addenda et corrigenda (Gastropoda, Stylommatophora)*. Muzeum i Instytut Zoologii PAN, Warszawa, 91 pp.
- RIEDEL A. & VILELLA M. 1968. Zur Kenntnis der Zonitidae (Gastropoda) Spaniens. *Miscelánea Zoológica*, 2 (3): 11-15.
- TURTON W 1840 *A manual of the land- and freshwater shells of the British Islands. A new edition*. Longman, Orme, Brown, Green, and Longmans: London, pp. 324, pl. 12.
- WELTER-SCHULTES F.W. 2012. *European non-marine molluscs, a guide for species identification*. Planet Poster Editions, Göttingen, 679 pp. + Q1-Q78 (of Quick identification plates).
- WELTER-SCHULTES F.W., AUDIBERT C. & BERTRAND A. 2011. Liste des mollusques terrestres et dulcicoles de France continentale (excl. hydrobioïdes). *Folia Conchylologica*, 12: 4-44.